

THE EFFECT OF OWNERSHIP STRUCTURE ON VOLUNTARY DISCLOSURE OF ANNUAL FINANCIAL REPORTS IN JORDAN COMPANIES

AMMAR ALMANSOUR¹, ALA HUSSEIN ALBAWWAT², BORHAN AL-DALAIEN³, AHMAD ALBLOUSH⁴, ALMONTASER QADORAH⁵, MO'TAZ AL ZOB⁶ and BILAL ZUREIGAT⁷

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7} Faculty of Business, Accounting Department, Amman Arab University (AAU), Amman 11953, Jordan.
*Correspondence: Email: bawwat_alaa@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of ownership structure on the level of voluntary disclosure by some chosen non-financial companies in Amman Stock Exchange (ASE). A total period of 10 years reports was considered annually between "2010 -2020" and the OLS-regression model was made to test study predictions in this research. The analysed data indicated a negative significant difference of voluntary disclosure level on the block holder ownership and managerial ownership which well-matched to the study predictions and some other related studies conducted in the past. The model further revealed a positive connectivity on both the companies' performance and proportion of institutional investor ownership. Furthermore, the regulators and policymakers have significant roles to play to the success of any institutional settings as the duo was seen to improve better the quality of financial disclosures with improved transparency level of financial reports among companies in Jordan. It was however concluded that, this study remains relevant in exposing the potentials of ownership structure of a company in improving voluntary disclosure with the tendency of promoting the interest of potential investors and better transparency.

Keywords: Ownership Structure, Voluntary Disclosure, Annual Reports, Amman Stock Exchange.

1. INTRODUCTION

The crisis in the financial sector brought about reluctant attitude for potential investors to invest in any way. It is important for investor to make proper inquiries of the companies they aimed to invest into before investing on any profit-making business. On this note, investors could tap whatever information is needed from the firm's financial reports by voluntarily disclosing information. From the work of Chobpichien (2008), the author explained the corporate voluntary disclosure to be an external approach of revealing reports through appropriate corporations and beyond the mandatory level and taking note of legal aspect and regulatory requirements. The level at which voluntary disclosure is increasing in various companies is becoming alarming throughout the globe. This therefore calls on various researchers to carry out substantive research capable to fully address some of the factors necessary to improve better the performance of a company in revealing tangible information (Al-Ajmi, 2009).

It is essential to know that voluntary disclosure serves as a useful tool to stakeholders in providing necessary data which could in turn lower or eradicate the level uncertainty and where a good and accurate decision making of economic finance is achieved as mentioned by Cooke

(1989). For an organization to add more values to the quality of investment and to sustain its economic system, it is important to take note of the level of transparency that could take place in corporate voluntary disclosure (CVD) level (Albawwat and Ali basah, 2015). As at 1970s, the CDV alongside with its determinants were seen to have attracted more attention from experts in the field of accounting. Scientific literature revealed several factors like the mechanisms of corporate governance (e.g., ownership structure and characteristics of firms) that are capable to impact voluntary disclosures. The logical and theoretical approach in such area of specialization made use of different theories to describe better the practices of voluntary disclosure and subsequently the manner at which the voluntary disclosure levels were affected like the case sample of agency theory from the work of Jensen & Meckling (1976), Legitimacy Theory by Dowling & Pfeffer (1975) and signalling theory by Connelly et al. (2011).

To determine the effect of CVD and ownership structure, many empirical trials have been proposed in both developing and developed economies. The limited empirical analysis from various studies in the past motivated us to go for this research so as to shed more light on the uncertainty arising this area of study in both developed and developing markets (Soliman, Ragab & Eldin, 2017). On this note, it was discovered that, different nations would have to operate on their markets in different ways simply because of the indifferences ascribed to both developing and developed markets.

According to the researchers, the diverse results of previous studies are likely attributable to differences in the contexts in which earlier studies were conducted, such as economic structure, accounting standards, capital market, legal and social environment. Chau & Gray (2002) caution that the implications of the connection amongst voluntary disclosure and its determinants that hold in one nation may not hold in another. Due to the differences in market characteristics of the Jordanian market compared to developed markets, acquiring empirical information on this topic from a small merging market (Jordan) is likely to contribute to the current research. In comparison to well-developed markets, Jordan's market is expected to have more concentrated ownership, poorer corporate governance systems, fewer protection of investors, lesser mergers and acquisitions activity, and lower disclosure quality. This study aims to enhance previous relevant studies by conducting scientific investigation in a small emerging market. More precisely, the study investigates the relationship between voluntary disclosures and the key characteristics of corporate governance systems experimentally. These are ownership structure (represented by block holder ownership, managerial ownership, and institutional ownership).

2. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In recent time, the CVD appears to be among the most critical factors to consider round the world considering the corporate reporting (Elfeky, 2017; Kolsi, 2017; Kamel & Awadallah, 2017; Zaini, at al., 2018; Masum, at al., 2020; Alqatameen, et al. 2020 and Tinh, 2021). Voluntary reporting is a concept of divulging corporate information by the business organization and at same time beyond a mandatory report level as mentioned by Dhaliwal et al. (2011). Again, according to Madi et al. (2014), voluntary disclosure was not only seen as

means of communication, but also served as a means of improving the reputation of a given firm (Abeysekera & Guthrie, 2005), by also attracting prospective or potential investors (Samaha et al., 2015). In a concise note, the agency theory also could demand for more voluntary information to be disclosed as this stands to be very crucial to the conflicting agency among people within the business system and other principal personalities (stallholders) as revealed by Jensen & Meckling (1976). Indeed, there are enormous benefits attached to corporate voluntary information due to its ability lower the level of malpractices of the financial institution which could in turn encourage the safety of investor (Kolsi, 2017). From another angle of agency theory, information asymmetry and the principal-agent relationship have been explained better when connecting the duo with other stakeholders of the companies (An et al., 2011). Again, it is expected to put into legal act of operation to divulge necessary voluntary data (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008). In line with the notion of legitimacy theory, business organization act on desirable system in accordance with the rules of law been established. in a given environment (Suchman, 1995). The legitimacy theory however could assume that a social treaty among the said environment and business organization by which a particular business is self-legalized in providing useful information to every member of the society in place as connoted from Cormier & Gordon (2001). Considering the above explanation, some element of similarities has been observed from the legitimacy theory and the agency theory and this appears to real also according to many scientific literature reviews on CVD.

In another spotlight of study, the CVD was seen to share better equity among various shareholders of a firm with regards to both capital and votes but also by the identification of the owners of equity, which thereby exerted more potential to control the power of people owning the equity. Additionally, the concept behind CVD was seen to be so crucial to the mechanism of corporate governance as this could impact in diverse way on the type of ownership structure in accordance to established rules, regulations and financing system been adopted by the firm as coined from La Porta et al. (1998). Diverse researchers from different part of the world established many findings how impactful an ownership structure could be with different themes of study line. But the end products of their results agreed to the fact that ownership structure truly contributed meaningfully to the development of business firms. To contribute more knowledge to literature, the current work is designed to investigate the effects of structural ownership of firms in Jordan considering the owner's identity of block holder ownership, ownership by management and ownership by institution.

2.1 Block Holder Ownership

Quite several scientific data revealed possible interaction among block holder ownership (BHO) and voluntary disclosure level. Part of the studies (McKinnon and Dalimunthe, 1993; Schadewitz and Blevins, 1998; Hossain et al. 1994; Chau and Gray, 2002; Haniffa and Cooke, 2002; Makhija and Patton, 2004; Huafang and Jianguo 2007; Grassa and Chakroun, 2016; Alfraih, 2018; Alqatameen, et al. 2020) revealed a positive significant difference between the BHO and voluntary disclosure level. Meanwhile the case was difference from other findings (Naser et al., 2002; Eng and Mak, 2003; Juhmani, 2017; Abdul Rahman and Hamdan, 2017, and Yamani, et al. 2021) where, there was no significant difference among the target factors.

Furthermore, the BHO has been observed to be negatively relationship and significant to voluntary disclosure as concluded from another group of researchers (Marston and Poley, 2004; Ismail and El-Shaib, 2012; Adelopo, 2011; Samaha et al., 2012). Their findings specifically established the fact that, the prominent wealthy shareholders were affected by the financial performance of selected firms, as the shareholders of the firms claimed to have possessed more level of personal authority and incentives to over control of the management as said by Jensen & Meckling (1976). In a different way, decentralisation of ownership structure has been argued to create more conflict of interest to the principal-agent (Fama& Jensen, 1983). To respond from another point of view, the works of the following researchers: (Shleifer and Vishny, 1986; Huddart, 1993; Noe 2002), made suggestion to integrate prominent shareholders to supervise necessary activities capable to tackle any arising conflict. It could therefore be possible to predict that managers could disclose better and necessary information from the annual reports of the firm as this will in turn minimize the cost of agency.

Basically, the term ownership simply means, investors that hold 5% or more of shares in a firm. The monitoring capacity of the shareholder can be increases by possessing a higher percentage of shares, and the resultant effect of this could influence behaviour of the managers. Therefore, the said managers are not expected to be moved freely toward their interests. It has been recommended that, companies with an intense ownership structure had poorer incentives toward voluntary disclosures. This is because shareholders had the tendency to tap directly useful information from the firms (Bushman, et al., 2004). Based on different empirical studies on ownership structure and BHO, it is obvious that there many irregularities and there is need to make more findings to see which part could be right. The block holders were seen to impact negatively on voluntary disclosers as mentioned by Juhmani (2013), Hieu & Lan (2015) and Kolsi (2017). Meanwhile the reverse is the case from the work of Huafang & Jianguo (2007) and Alhazaimh et al. (2013). But another study finding concluded on the inability of at BHO to have impact on voluntary disclosure level (Eng & Mak, 2003; Donnelly & Mulcahy, 2008). The present study however predicts that, BHO is negatively relationship on voluntary disclosure level.

H1: The extent of voluntary disclosure is negatively related with the block holder ownership.

2.2 Managerial Ownership (MO)

The Managerial ownership (MO) is defined as the ratio in which shares owned by the executives and CEOs of the firm. Nevertheless, ownership stands to be a critical factor to consider for the agency problems as the control could be made to increasing the MO for their interest to be given proper recognition together with other stakeholders. According to Mgammal (2017), it is important to note that, in case of any fall of MO, external shareholders is needed to be frequently monitored the manager's behaviours. In an effort to cut down the cost arising from external shareholders, it is expected from the manager to supply voluntary disclosure information which remains optional. Additionally, it has been disclosed that, ownership structure in expanded Australian companies significantly affected the proportion of voluntary disclosure (McKinnon and Dalimunthe, 1993). It should be noted that, when in agency cost decreases, this brings about increasing level in MO. Therefore, the information

disclosure request to screen manager could be minimized. On a clearer note, the management status of a firm is improved only if their ownership structure increases as well. Meanwhile the management can make use internal information for the sake of their own benefits with the main aim of attaining certain goals, reduced transparency of information (Mgammal, 2017).

Briefly, the MO was identified as the proportions at which of shares are owned by top notch managers (division supervisors and directors). It was argued that management possess full capacity to adopt malpractices, as they opportune to have access to every kind of items disclosure in the companies and they are equally competent to decide on which items to disclose to other parties. This signifies unethical behaviour that could affect the overall performance of the company. More so, the implication here is that management could not be seen motivated in enhancing disclosure. The results from previous findings revealed the provision of less voluntary information by higher managerial ownership (Huafang & Jianguo, 2007; Beak, Johanson & Kim, 2009; Akhtaruddin & Haron, 2010; Putra, et al. 2020 and Alqatameen, et al. 2020). The case was different from another study where the MO did not affect the voluntary disclosure level (Juhmani, 2013 and Siala, & Moalla, 2017). The current research is trying to predict that MO is negatively related to the voluntary disclosure level. The hypothesis below is revealed:

H2: The extent of voluntary disclosure is negatively associated with the managerial ownership.

2.3 Institutional Ownership (IO)

The IO was recognised as a shareholding possessing higher level of shares according to Masum, at al., (2020). The IO is commonly found in developing nations where they were seen to respond efficiently to a reasonable number of institutional issues because of the unstable nature of organisation with poor infrastructural facilities development in the domain of developing nation (Elango et al., 2016). In line with the agency theory, where business structure is characterised with single ownership and low proportion of shares are attached to many investors of a given firm. Companies are expected to disclose better information so as to meet up with the satisfactory level of investors (Marston & Polei, 2004). However, the investor of an organization has more tendencies to satisfy themselves with more confidential information from the firms by directly communicating with the firms in question (Kolsi, 2017). A contrary relationship is expected to be observed between the IO and the level voluntary disclosure. On the theory of legitimacy, legal business is an integral part of the society and useful information is expected to be disclosed or shared with the society as revealed from the work of Cormier & Gordon (2001). Nevertheless, shareholders of the companies could have access to the information within an internal system of the company (Masum, at al., 2020), and this could restrict minor shareholders to access possible available information which could lead to poor power of bargaining. A positive correlation has been seen to exist between IO and corporate voluntary disclosures based on empirical studies carried out in some selected advanced countries like: Finland (Schadewitz & Blevins, 1998) Australia (Mitchell et al., 1995) and in Germany (Marston & Polei, 2004). On the other hand, a mixed research findings have been seen growing nations as conducted by Kolsi (2017) and Nguyen et al. (2020). The work of Aljifri et al. (2014) postulated a positive significant difference between the IO and corporate

disclosure level based on the condition that, the shareholders of the institution are ranging from 5% to 10% of all the equity. From a case sample of study carried out in Egypt, a negative significant difference was observed among the duo (Elfeky, 2017 and Habtoor, et al. 2020). Likewise in Abu Dhabi, similar findings were revealed by Kolsi (2017), but no significant difference was seen in research conducted in Tunisia while (Kolsi, 2012), in Saudi Arabian (Alnabshaet al. 2018) and in Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) (Yamani, et al. 2021). Past research findings remain inconclusive thereby led to the hypothesis below:

H3: The extent of voluntary disclosure is negatively associated with the institutional ownership.

3. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

3.1 Data

A total of 240 companies are known to be registered under the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) which has been assigned to 3 basic sectors (Financial, Services and Industry). The area of financial sector has not been considered due to the mechanisms action of corporate governance and firms dealing with finance that are seen to be in need of various application (albawwat et al., 2020). Concisely, series of rule and regulations are known to set aright the activities financial firms so as to deliver the best results as coined from Marashdeh (2014) and Albawwat et al. (2020). On this note, diverse techniques of policy making process can be adopted structure and established better the financial and non-financial sector of the firm.

The current study made used of 2 different sectors (services and industry) from the ASE where a sample population of 150 Jordanian were considered (60% ASE of registered firms). In detail, industry sector consisted of 80 companies (representing 32% of ASE registered firms) and the service sector considered 70 services (accountable of 28% of ASE listed firms). Obviously ten companies were chosen for the study sampling with 4 firms from industry sector and 6 firms from services. However, 140 firms have been considered for investigation from the year 2010 to 2020 (making 10 years). A secondary data of financial reports was gathered annually by sourcing them from the ASE's website.

3.2 Voluntary Disclosure index

More than average of firms chooses to reveal both financial and non-financial information to investors voluntarily alongside with some concern stakeholders by means of yearly financial reports. Disclosing such information could serve the purpose of providing reasonable information on the performance of the firms and to pass across some of established decisions by the management. Based on this, multiple factors were seen to affect the voluntary disclosure level which brought about the idea of carrying out this study. A descriptive analytical and theoretical approaches is adopted for a series of theoretical study capable to describe better the practices of voluntary disclosure (agency theory as a case sample) (Jensen & Meckling, 1976); legitimacy theory as adopted by Dowling & Pfeffer (1975) and signalling theory by Connelly et al. (2011). The ownership structure has been found to gain more attention from another angle of empirical research where this could have effect on corporate voluntary disclosure and the mechanism of corporate governance in developing and advanced economies. It is not doubtful

that as series of literatures has discuss much on VDI vis-à-vis from the work of Ghazali & Weetman, (2006); Lim et al. (2007) and Haddad, et al. (2009). Considering the work of Haddad et al. (2009) and Chau & Gray (2010), a self -structured index was adopted based on compiled items been disclosed voluntary from firms in Jordan. A total of 64 disclosure items were considered from previous studies on voluntary disclosure by observing all items against requirements of regulatory disclosures in the past one decade. This was maintained solidly to be important for structuring VDI suitable for Jordanian business environment. It was noted, previous studies on disclosure made use of some items that were not included as they are part of the policies of ASE, but they were later re introduced. At long run, we concluded upon 54 items of information. These information items were obtained directly by hand from the yearly reports of the companies from 2015 to 2019. Considering the studies protocols of Meek, at al. (1995); Allaya et al. (2018), this research makes use of a disclosure index. To score the items of information a dichotomous approach was used, in which a score of zero (0) for undisclosed item and score one (1) stood for disclosed item as applicable to the company. Various reasons have been revealed not to allocate weight to disclosure item (Meek et al., 1995). Firstly, weighting based on assessment of subjective, secondly weighing assigned to a number of items discloser which could not reflect on the preference of other financial statement users. And finally, the better the DVI the more of neglecting unnecessary items it becomes (Allaya, et al., 2018).

A voluntary disclosure index is a ratio or percentage of a company's reflect the effectiveness divided by the total number of the items that the company is required to reveal in yearly financial reports (i.e., VD 56 items). In other words, each item was given a score of 1 if it was disclosed in annual financial reports and a score of 0 if it was not. The scores for each item were added together to give each company a final score, and the voluntary disclosure index was calculated as the ratio of total items disclosed divided by the total number possible score.

3.3 Definitions of Variables

Table1: Definitions of the variables.

VARIABLE	ACRONYM	MEASUREMENT
Dependent Variables		
Voluntary disclosure index	VDI	Dichotomous variables – one for each disclosing item otherwise zero.
Independent Variables		
Block holder ownership	BLOCK	The percentage of ordinary shares owned by substantial shareholders (5% or more).
Managerial ownership	MOWN	The proportion of shares owned by mangers (I. e. the CEO and inside directors).
Institutional ownership	INSTOW	Total number of institutional shareholdings scaled by total shareholding.
Control variables		
Company Size	COSIZE	The company's total assets.
The ratio gearing	GEAR	Long term debt/ the equity.
Profitability	ROE	Net income/total equity.

3.4 Model Development

The regression model of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was employed to observe the relationship among variables that are dependent and independent variables. The equation below represents the design model:

$$VDI_{it} = a_0 + \beta_1 BLOCK_{it} + \beta_2 MOWN_{it} + \beta_3 INSTOW_{it} + \beta_4 COSIZE_{it} + \beta_5 GEAR_{it} + \beta_6 ROE_{it}$$

Where, VDI = Voluntary disclosure index received by each sample firm's; α_0 = the constant, ϵ_{it} = the error term, β_1 to β_7 = the coefficients of the variables defined in Table 1, and 'i' and 't' = the number of firms and period in that order.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

This study made use of reliable data obtained from Jordan and the outputs from a descriptive statistical analysis of 3 variables (control, dependent and independent) are observed in Table 2. The mean values of voluntary disclosure level from the sample companies are 0.42 representing 42% with a least value of 0.32 and 0.62 for the highest value. Similar range of findings has been observed accordingly in Greece from the works of Leventis and Weetman (2004) with a percentage value of 37%, also in Kuwait (46%) by Al-Shammari (2008) and in Malaysia (31%) by Ghazali and Weetman (2006). Referring to the descriptive statistical analysis of variables data, the highest mean value level of 0.31 (31%) was obviously seen under BLOCK (block holder ownership). More than the average level ownership felt within the institutional investors (INSTOW) with a mean value of 0.61 as 0.27 was recorded under the managerial ownership (MOWN).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for the Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
VDI Score	140	0.32	0.62	0.42	0.0544391
BLOCK	140	0.013	0.788	0.3106862	0.2165791
MOWN	140	0.00	1.00	0.2758621	0.4495387
INSTOW	140	0.05	0.888	0.61087	0.213798
COSIZE	140	6.150351	8.532287	7.811388	0.4490769
GEAR	140	0.42204	0.9230837	0.2619633	0.242815
ROE	140	-0.311111	0.35382	0.1029932	0.1222853

4.2 Correlations

It is noted from Table 3 to represent the correlation matrix for both dependent and continuous variables. Based on correlation test, the results indicated a negative significant difference of voluntary disclosure level with the BLOCK. Variables that are considered to be dependent propelled a correlation test to be significantly positive with INSTOW. This implied that, firms

characterised by higher level of institutional ownership were highly motivated to disclose more information voluntary compared to other firms of low level of institutional ownership. Considering the independent variables, the highest mean value (0.4146) of correlation was observed between institutional ownership and the rate at which profit are made. Of all the independent variables, a relatively low correlation manifested which agreed to the work of Bryman and Cramer (1997). It was however suggested that things must not be considered harmful when simple correlation do exist among the factors of independent variables, until when the exceeded 0.80 or 0.90. The correlation test therefore revealed less worries as the firms could be free from correlation.

Table 3: The Pearson Correlation Results

	VDI	BLOCK	MOWN	INSTOW	COSIZE	GEAR	ROE
VDI	1						
BLOCK	-.76*	1					
MOWN	-.28	.18	1				
INSTOW	.42**	-.32***	-.24***	1			
COSIZE	.22	-.31***	-.08	.14	1		
GEAR	-.48**	.35***	.15	.32***	-.03	1	
ROE	.44**	-.37***	.04	.41**	-.04	.22	1
***Correlation is significant at the 0.01level.							
**Correlation is significant at the 0.05level.							
*Correlation is significant at the 0.10level.							

4.3 Regression Results

As presented in Table 4, the model of OLS regression was statistically employed to determine possible impact of ownership structure (OS) on voluntary disclosure where six variables were considered. Thus, an average value of 68.43% of the variance was recorded in line with the disclosure of voluntary in Jordanian firm. This sample data is acceptable according to international standard (Pallant, 2001). More so, a mean significant value of less than 1% (0.000) was recorded from the overall analysed data. However, the statistical analysis revealed a strong significant difference on the ability of OS to affect the level of VD.

Table 4: The Effect of Ownership Structure on Voluntary Disclosure.

Variables	Coefficients	P-value
BLOCK	-0.145	0.000***
MOWN	-0.016	0.04**
INSTOW	0.018	0.335
COSIZE	0.002	0.800
GEAR	-0.044	0.005***
ROE	0.070	0.040**
R squared	0.684	
R squared adjustment	0.660	
F-statistics	28.90	
Probability. (F-statistics)	0.000	
***Correlation is significant at the 0.01level.		
**Correlation is significant at the 0.05level.		
*Correlation is significant at the 0.10level.		

The output data from Table 4 supported hypothesis one (H1) and indicated the relevance block holder ownership, ability for companies to disclose less the information of voluntary compared to disclosers of firms with lesser or single OS. Conversely, the block holder ownership was seen to impact negatively based on the activity's voluntary disclosure level where p value was less than 0.05. This negative claim of relationship between block ownership and disclosure agreed to the work of Mitchell et al. (1995) and Schadewitz and Blevins (1998). Scientific literature review from past studies equally brought to book many evidence on how the block holder ownership could negatively impact on the level of disclosure in both developing and developed countries. As case sample from Australia by McKinnon & Dalimun the (1993) and Mitchell & al. (1995).Also, in Finland and Germany by Schadewitz & Blevins (1998) and Marston & Polei (2004) respectively. Nevertheless, some authors from Malaysia (Hossain & al., 1994) and Egyptian (Samaha et al., 2012) equally addressed their views.

Based on regression coefficient of managerial ownership (MOWN), a negative significant difference was observed where $p < 0.05$. This therefore supported second hypothesis (H2) negative relationship of managerial ownership to the voluntary disclosure level. Coincidentally, similar results from previous research works were found by Eng & Mak (2003); Beak, Johanson & Kim (2009) and Rouf & Al Harun (2011). On the other way round by considering the institutional ownership (INSTOW), the test of regression coefficient indicated a p value of 0.335 which is higher than 0.05 revealing no significant effect between the institutional ownership (INSTOW) and voluntary disclosure level of sample population of the

companies selected for the research. On this note, the antagonistic reaction from the third hypothesis (H3) which is therefore rejected by accepting alternative hypothesis, making comparison with previous research, this claim was found to be in line with the works Chau & Gray (2002); Lim, et al. (2007) and Sartawi, et al. (2014) where the authors also revealed no significant difference.

The analysed impact of control variables (CV) signified that; bigger companies are always characterised by higher the disclosure of voluntary level. The evidence of empirical that spring out from the approach of regression model revealed a clear relationship between level of profitability and the level of voluntary disclosure based on yearly reports of selected firms. Since p-value (0.05) was found to be equal to 0.05, this explains why the coefficient regression establishes the fact that the profitability level is determining factor capable to directly influence level of voluntary disclosure Jordanian companies. It should however be noted that, a negative relationship existed from voluntary disclosure level and the level of gearing ratio based on the statistical relationship of the regression coefficients model which could have been due to unequal data of information from different companies.

Voluntary disclosure is indeed implemented by ASE listed businesses in Jordan in its annual reports, as evidenced by the study's findings. The firms' level of transparency, on the other hand, is still regarded low. Yet, based on the information obtained within the period specified (2015-2019). However, the results of this study can indeed be useful to a wide range of people. The current research results can firstly offer companies with a knowledge of their own existing voluntary disclosure procedures. As such, companies might improve to attain more disclosure and transparency. Secondly, the results of the present study might help other users understand the aspects of an enterprise's voluntary disclosure. In addition, regulators like the ASE and JSC might also review the conclusions of the study to improve the voluntary disclosure practices of the businesses listed in ASE in Jordan. In addition, this study suggests making some disclosure elements obligatory. Business strategy, financial ratios, future opportunities, performance indicators, research and development, social policy, and stock price information are among these elements (in no particular order).

5. CONCLUSION

For the success of any companies in Jordan, it is important to note that the voluntary disclosure (VD) remains a crucial tool of control for the fact that, it could provide more and better transparency, sufficient information to shareholders by also protecting their interests. This therefore makes companies to be more conscious of their reputation. As a matter of fact, firms are motivated with the aim of improving better their level of VDs.

This study successfully investigated impactful effect of ownership structure (OS) on corporate voluntary disclosure (CVD) considering listed samples of firms in Jordan. An exploration of differences between block holder ownership, institutional investor ownership, the level of voluntary disclosure and managerial ownership was done under a controlled impact of company's debt, firm's size, and profitability on equity. The study then concluded that, block holder ownership negatively had affected as the level of voluntary disclosure increases. We

equally discovered that the managerial ownership was negatively related with the voluntary disclosure level. Conversely, as the institutional investor ownership increases lead to an increasing level of voluntary disclosure.

Based on the outcome of this study, it is imperative for policymakers, researchers, and regulators to be aware of the fundamental benefits of financial disclosure in Jordan. Finally, future research can direct towards other financial institution like insurance firms, banks, and real estate with the using updated, reliable, and suitable disclosure index.

References

- Abdul Rahman, Azhar, and Mohd DiahHamdan. (2017). the Extent of Compliance with FRS 101 Standard: Malaysian Evidence. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research* 18: 87–115.
- Abeysekera, I., & Guthrie, J. (2005). An empirical investigation of annual reporting trends of intellectual capital in Sri Lanka. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 16(3), 151-163.
- Adelopo, I (2011). Voluntary Disclosure Practices amongst Listed Companies in Nigeria. *Advances in Accounting*. Vol.27 (2), 338-345.
- Akhtaruddin, M., &Haron, H. (2010). Board ownership, audit committees' effectiveness, and corporate voluntary disclosures. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 18(3), 245-259.
- Al-Ajmi, J. (2009). Investors' use of corporate reports in Bahrain. *Managerial Auditing Journal*. Vol.24 (3).266-28.
- Albawwat, A. H., & Ali Basah, M. (2015). Corporate governance and voluntary disclosure of interim financial reporting in Jordan. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 5(2), 100-127.
- Albawwat, A. H., Almansour, A., & Alrawashedh, N. H. (2020). The Effect of Board of Directors and Audit Committee Characteristics on Company Performance in Jordan. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 11(6), 10-24.
- Alfraih, Mishari. (2018). the Role of Corporate Governance in Intellectual Capital Disclosure. *International Journal of Ethics and Systems* 34: 101–21.
- Alhazaimah, A., Palaniappan, R., & Almsafir, M. (2013). The Impact of Corporate governance and Ownership Structure on Voluntary Disclosure in Annual Reports among Listed Jordanian Companies. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 341-348.
- Aljifri, K., Alzarouni, A., Ng, C., & Tahir, M. I. (2014). The association between firm characteristics and corporate financial disclosures: evidence from UAE companies. *The International Journal of Business and Finance Research*, 8(2), 101-123.
- Allaya, M., Derouiche, I., & Muesig, A. (2018). Voluntary Disclosure, Ownership Structure, and Corporate Debt Maturity: A study on French Firms. *International review of financial analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2018.12.008>
- Alnabsha, A., Abdou, H. A., Ntim, C. G., & Elamer, A. A. (2018). Corporate boards, ownership structures and corporate disclosures: Evidence from a developing country. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 19(1), 20-41.
- Alqatameen, D. E., Alkhalaleh, M. A. A., & Dabaghia, M. N. (2020). Ownership Structure, Board Composition and Voluntary Disclosure by Nonfinancial firms listed In (ASE). *International Business Research*, 13(7), 93-107. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v13n7p93>

- Al-Shammari, B. (2008). Voluntary disclosure in Kuwait corporate annual reports. *Review of business research*. Vol.8 (1). 62- 81.
- An, Y., Davey, H., & Eggleton, I. R. (2011). Towards a comprehensive theoretical framework for voluntary IC disclosure. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 12(4), 571-585.
- Beak, Y., Johnson, D., & Kim, J. (2009). Managerial Ownership, Corporate Governance and Voluntary Disclosure. *Journal of Business and Economic Studies*, 15(2), 44.
- Beak, Y., Johnson, D., & Kim, J. (2009). Managerial Ownership, Corporate Governance and Voluntary Disclosure. *Journal of Business and Economic Studies*, 15(2), 44.
- Branco, M. C., & Rodrigues, L. L. (2008). Factors influencing social responsibility disclosure by Portuguese companies. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 83(4), 685-701.
- Bryman, A. and Cramer, D. (1997). *Quantitative data analysis with SPSS for windows*. London: Routledge.
- Bushman, R., Chen, Q., Engel, E., & Smith, A. (2004). Financial Accounting Information, Organizational Complexity and Corporate Governance System. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 37(2), 167-201 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2003.09.005>
- Chau, G. K., & Gray, S. J. (2002). Ownership structure and corporate voluntary disclosure in Hong Kong and Singapore. *The International Journal of Accounting*. Vol.37(2), 247-265.
- Chobpichien, J. (2008). *The Quality of Board of Directors, Ownership Structure and Level of Voluntary Disclosure of Listed Companies in Thailand*. PhD thesis, Universiti Sains Malaysia.
- Cooke, T.E. (1989). Disclosure in the corporate annual reports of Swedish companies. *Accounting and business research*. Vol.19 (74). 113-124.
- Cormier, D., & Gordon, I. M. (2001). An examination of social and environmental reporting strategies. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 14(5), 587-617.
- Cormier, D., Ledoux, M. & Magnan, M. (2011). The Informational Contribution of Social and Environmental Disclosures for Investors. *Management Decision*. Vol. 49(8): 1276-1304.
- Dhaliwal, D. S., Li, O. Z., Tsang, A., & Yang, Y. G. (2011). Voluntary nonfinancial disclosure and the cost of equity capital: The initiation of corporate social responsibility reporting. *The Accounting Review*, 86(1), 59-100.
- Donnelly, R., & Mulcahy, M. (2008). Board structure, ownership, and voluntary disclosure in Ireland. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 16(5), 416-429.
- Dowling, J., & Pfeffer, J. (1975). Organizational legitimacy: Social values and organizational behavior. *Pacific sociological review*. Vol.5 (1)122-136.
- Elango, B., Pattnaik, C., & Wieland, J. R. (2016). Do business group characteristics matter? An exploration on the drivers of performance variation. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(9), 3205-3212.
- Elfeky, M. I. (2017). The extent of voluntary disclosure and its determinants in emerging markets: Evidence from Egypt. *The Journal of Finance and Data Science*, 3(1-4), 45-59.
- Eng, L. L., & Mak, Y. T. (2003). Corporate governance and voluntary disclosure. *Journal of accounting and public policy*. Vol.22 (4).325-345.
- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of law and economics*. Vol.4 (5)301-325.
- Ghazali, N. A. M., & Weetman, P. (2006). Perpetuating traditional influences: Voluntary disclosure in Malaysia following the economic crisis. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 15(2), 226-248.

- Grassa, Rihab, and RaidaChakroun. (2016). Ownership Structure, Board's Characteristics and Corporate Governance Disclosure in GCC Banks: What about Islamic Banks? *International Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Performance Evaluation* 12: 360–95.
- Habtoor, O. S., Hassan, W. K., &Aljaaidi, K. S. (2019). The impact of corporate ownership structure on corporate risk disclosure: Evidence from the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 15(2), 325-356. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/beh.2019.20>
- Haddad, A. E., AlShattarat, W. K., &Nobanee, H. (2009). Voluntary disclosure and stock market liquidity: evidence from the Jordanian capital market. *International Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Performance Evaluation*, 5(3), 285-309.
- Haniffa, R. M., & Cooke, T. E. (2002). Culture, Corporate Governance and Disclosure in Malaysian corporations. *Abacus*, 38(3), 317-349.
- Hieu, N., &Lan, D. (2015). Factors Influencing the Voluntary Disclosure of Vietnamese Listed Companies. *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, 11(12), 656-676.
- Hossain, M., Tan, L. M., & Adams, M. (1994). Voluntary disclosure in an emerging capital market: Some empirical evidence from companies listed on the Kuala Lumpur Stock Exchange. *The International Journal of Accounting*. Vol.29 (4).334–351.
- Huafang, X., &Jianguo, Y. (2007). Ownership structure, board composition and corporate voluntary disclosure: Evidence from listed companies in China. *Managerial Auditing Journal*. Vol.22 (6).604-619.
- Huddart, S. (1993). The effect of a large shareholder on corporate value. *Management Science*. Vol.39 (11). 1407-1421.
- Ismail, T. H., & El-Shaib, N. M. (2012). Impact of market and organizational determinants on voluntary disclosure in Egyptian companies. *Meditari Accountancy Research*. Vol.20 (2). 113-133.
- Jensen, M. C., &Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of financial economics*. Vol.3 (4), 305-360.
- Juhmani, O. (2013). Ownership Structure and Corporate Voluntary Disclosure: Evidence from Bahrain. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 3(2), 133-148. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijaf.v3i2.4088>
- Juhmani, Omar. (2017). Corporate Governance and the Level of Bahraini Corporate Compliance with IFRS Disclosure. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research* 18: 22–41.
- Kamel, H., &Awadallah, E. (2017). The extent of voluntary corporate disclosure in the Egyptian stock exchange: its determinants and consequences. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 7(2), 266-291.
- Kolsi, M. C. (2012). The determinants of corporate voluntary disclosure: evidence from the Tunisian capital market. *The IUP Journal of Accounting Research and Audit Practices*, 11(4), 49-68.
- Kolsi, M. C. (2017). The determinants of corporate voluntary disclosure policy: Evidence from the Abu Dhabi Securities Exchange (ADX). *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 7(2), 249-265.
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., &Vishny, R. W. (1998). Law and Finance. *Journal of Political Economy*, 106(6), 1113-1155. <https://doi.org/10.1086/250042>
- Leventis, S., &Weetman, P. (2004). Voluntary disclosures in an emerging capital market: some evidence from the Athens Stock Exchange. *Advances in International Accounting*, 17, 227-250.
- Lim, S., Matolcsy, Z., & Chow, D. (2007). The Association between board composition and different types of voluntary disclosure. *European accounting Review*, 16(3), 555-583. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638180701507155>

- Madi, H. K., Ishak, Z., & Manaf, N. A. A. (2014). The impact of audit committee characteristics on corporate voluntary disclosure. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 164, 486-492.
- Makhija, A. K., & Patton, J. M. (2004). The Impact of Firm Ownership Structure on Voluntary Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Czech Annual Reports. *The Journal of Business*. Vol.77 (3). 457-491.
- Marashdeh, Z. M. S. (2014). The Effect of Corporate Governance on Firm Performance in Jordan. (Ph.D thesis), University of Central Lancashire.
- Marston, C., & Polei, A. (2004). Corporate reporting on the Internet by German companies. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*. Vol.5 (3). 285-311.
- MASUM, M. H., LATIFF, A. R. A., & OSMAN, M. N. H. (2020). Ownership Structure and Corporate Voluntary Disclosures in Transition Economy. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(10), 601–611. <https://doi.org/10.13106/JAFEB.2020.VOL7.NO10.601>
- McKinnon, J. L., & Dalimunthe, L. (1993). Voluntary disclosure of segment information by Australian diversified companies. *Accounting & Finance*. Vol.33 (1). 33-50.
- Meeke, G., Gray, S., & Roberts, C. (1995). International Capital Market Pressures and Voluntary Annual Report Disclosures by U.S. and U.K. Multinationals. *Journal of International Financial Management & Accounting*, 6(1), 43-68.
- Mgammal, M. H. (2017) The Effect of Ownership Structure on Voluntary Disclosure: Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Advanced Management Science* Vol. 5, No. 2, doi: 10.18178/joams.5.2.138-151.
- Mitchell, J. D., Chia, C. W., & Loh, A. S. (1995). Voluntary disclosure of segment information: Further Australian evidence. *Accounting & Finance*, 35(2), 1-16.
- Mitchell, J. D., Chia, C. W., & Loh, A. S. (1995). Voluntary disclosure of segment information: Further Australian evidence. *Accounting & Finance*, 35(2), 1-16.
- Naser, K., Al-Khatib, K., & Karbhari, Y. (2002). Empirical evidence on the depth of corporate information disclosure in developing countries: the case of Jordan. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*. Vol.12 (3/4). 122-155.
- Nguyen, T. M. H., Nguyen, N. T., & Nguyen, H. T. (2020). Factors Affecting Voluntary Information Disclosure on Annual Reports: Listed Companies in Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 7(3), 53-62.
- Noe, T. H. (2002). Investor activism and financial market structure. *Review of Financial Studies*. Vol.15 (1). 289-318.
- Pallant, J. (2001). *SPSS survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using SPSS* (First edition). Buckingham: Open University Press.
- Putra, W.E, Kusuma, I.L, & Dewi, M.W. (2020). firm characteristic, ownership structure and voluntary disclosure: a study of Indonesian listed manufacturing firm. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research*, Vol.4 (2), E-ISSN: 2614-1280 P-ISSN 2622-4771.
- Rouf, A., & Al Harun, A. (2011). Ownership Structure and Voluntary Disclosure in Annual Reports of Bangladesh. *Pak. J. Commer. Soc. Sci*, 5(1), 129-139.
- Samaha, K., Dahawy, K., Hussainey, K., & Stapleton, P. (2012). The extent of corporate governance disclosure and its determinants in a developing market: The case of Egypt. *Advances in Accounting*. Vol.28 (1). 168-178.
- Samaha, K., Khelif, H., & Hussainey, K. (2015). The impact of board and audit committee characteristics on voluntary disclosure: A meta-analysis. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 24, 13-28.

Sartawi, I. I. S. M., Hindawi, R. M., Bsoul, R., & Ali, A. J. (2014). Board Composition, Firm Characteristics, and Voluntary Disclosure: The Case of Jordanian Firms Listed on the Amman Stock Exchange. *International Business Research*, 7(6). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v7n6p67>

Schadewitz, H. J., & Blevins, D. R. (1998). Major determinants of interim disclosures in an emerging market. *American Business Review*. Vol.16(1), 41-55.

Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1986). Large shareholders and corporate control. *The Journal of Political Economy*. Vol.94 (3). 461.

Siala, H. G., & Moalla, M... (2017). the effect of ownership structure on voluntary disclosure of intellectual capital information: the case of Canadian firms. *International Journal of Development Research*, Vol. 07, Issue, 01, pp.11044-11054.

Soliman, M. M., Ragab, A. A., & Eldin, M. B. (2014). Board composition, ownership structure and voluntary disclosure: An empirical study of the listed companies in Egypt. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 11(2-4), 415-426.

Suchman, M. C. (1995). Managing legitimacy: Strategic and institutional approaches. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), 571-610.

Tran QuocThinh (2021). The impact of firm characteristics on the voluntary disclosure – evidence on the top 50 listed firms of Forbes Vietnam. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 18(1), 215-222. doi:10.21511/imfi.18 (1).2021.18

Yamani, A., Khaled, H., and Khaldoun, A. (2021). Does Governance Affect Compliance with IFRS 7? *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 14: 239. <https://doi.org/10.3390/>.

Zaini, S. M., Samkin, G., Sharma, U., & Davey, H. (2018). Voluntary disclosure in emerging countries: a literature review. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 8(1), 29-65. doi: 10.1108/JAEE-08-2016-0069